

Speed-Flow-Density relationship of traffic movement in urban area: A case study

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ABSTRACT

Relationship between speed-flow-density of the traffic in Indian urban road has been conducted. Four parameters, namely, speed, flow, density and volume, have been considered while carrying out the study. Speed and density or concentration, which describe the quality of service experienced by the stream; and the flow and volume, which measures the quantity of the stream and the demand on the road facility. The relationship between speed, flow and density is widely varies from place to place, time to time. Indian roads are consisting of heterogeneous traffic which makes the situation harsher compared to the foreign countries. Kancharapar, an urban area of North 24 District, India has been selected as the case study area. Various types of survey, i.e. Manual and Video Graphic surveys have been conducted in the selected location for data collection. The data collected later decoded on the computer. This data is very essential to estimate capacity of an Indian road. Since the collected data is of a narrow density domain, capacity prediction from this data is not promising. Also, this independent work tests that the data provided confirms the volume-speed and density-speed relationships for uninterrupted traffic flow.

KEYWORDS- *urban area, speed-flow-density relationship, traffic movement, heterogeneous traffic, traffic survey*

1. INTRODUCTION

Traffic Flow depends upon the driver's movement and the interactions done by the vehicles in between two points. We cannot predict the traffic flow only by the driver's movement, which is more difficult to analyze. The basic parameters of traffic flow are speed, density and flow, which are most essential to know before understanding the vehicle flow. With the above three parameters we can design, plan and operate the roadway facility.

- **Speed:** In traffic engineering speed is defined as the distance travelled by a vehicle over a certain period. It's quite impossible to calculate the speed of every individual vehicle and due to this the average speed is considered. Average speed can be calculated in two ways. They are time mean speed and space mean speed. Time mean speed is defined as the average speed of vehicles crossing a particular section. Space means speed is defined in the following manners and space mean speed is defined as the ratio of distance (length) of section and the average time of vehicles crossing that section. Units: S.I. unit is m/sec and C.G.S. unit is cm/sec.

- **Flow:** It is defined as the ratio of the number of vehicles crossing a particular section and the time taken by the vehicle to cross that section. Units: vehicles/time.

- **Density:** After a particular time, the number of vehicles which occupy the region is defined as density. The density is generally averaged over a certain duration of time. Units: vehicles/distance.

- **Speed-Flow-Density relationship:** Relationships among Speed, Flow and Density are shown below in graphical format.

1.1. Speed-Density relationship:

The relation between speed and density is shown below in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: Speed-density diagram

Source: S. K. Khanna and C. E. G. Justo, “Highway Engineering,” Nem Chand & Bros, Roorkee, 2001

From the diagram it is very clear that the speed will be maximum when the density is zero or the vehicles flowing with the free flow speed. When the speed is zero then from the diagram it is clear that the density is maximum. From the figure the variation of speed with the density is linear in shape which can be represented in solid line in Fig. 1. When the density becomes jam density then the speed of vehicles is clearly zero.

1.2. Speed-Flow relationship:

The relation between speed and density is shown below in Fig. 2.

Figure 2: Speed-flow diagram

Source: S. K. Khanna and C. E. G. Justo, “Highway Engineering,” Nem Chand & Bros, Roorkee, 2001

The relation in between speed and flow can be explained as follows. If there are no vehicles or there are so many vehicles in such a position that they cannot move, then the flow is considered to be zero. The flow becomes maximum when the speed is either zero or free flow speed. This relationship can be seen clearly from the Fig. 2. At speed u the maximum flow Q_{max} occurs. For a given flow there can be two different speeds.

1.3. Flow-Density relationship:

The relation between speed and density is shown below in Fig. 3.

Figure 3: Flow density curve

Source: S. K. Khanna and C. E. G. Justo, “Highway Engineering,” Nem Chand & Bros, Roorkee, 2001

Time and location are the factors for the variation of flow and density. From the figure we can find the relation between the flow and density and some of the characteristics are mentioned below.

- i. When there are no vehicles on the road then the density is zero and automatically the flow is zero.
- ii. The density and flow will increase when the number of vehicles increases on the road stretch.
- iii. If vehicles go on increasing, then the vehicles can't move which is known as maximum density or jam density. The flow is zero at the position of jam density because vehicles are not moving.
- iv. When the flow is maximum then the density is jamming density or maximum density. From the figure the relation is in parabolic shape as shown in figure 3

From the figure the point O refers as zero density and zero flow. The maximum flow occurs at point B where the corresponding density is jam density. At point C the flow is zero and the density is jam density or maximum density. A tangent OA is drawn to the parabola and the slope can be found out which gives the speed with which a vehicle passes on the road stretch when the flow is zero. For the same flow there can be two different densities which can be seen from figure and the respective points are D and E. The mean speed at density k_1 can be calculated from the slope of the line OD and similarly the mean speed at density k_2 can be found out from the slope of the line. It is very clear that the speed at density k_1 is higher due to less number of vehicles on the road stretch.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Greenshield Model is the basic form of speed flow density relationship which paves the way for other researchers to find different types of speed flow density relationships for different types of roads. Greenberg also applied law of continuity and applied fluid dynamic principles to derive relation between speed, density and volume and developed logarithmic relation b/w speed and density. This model is unsuitable for low density roads as density tends to zero, speed tends to infinity [1].

K. M. Lum et al (1998) presented in his paper "SPEED-FLOW MODELING OF ARTERIAL ROADS IN SINGAPORE" modelled speed flow density relationship for radial and ring arterial roads in Singapore by taking minimum delay per intersection and no. of intersections per km as modal parameters [2].

Jomy Thomas et al (2011) in his paper "Vehicle Class Wise Speed-Volume Models For Heterogenous Traffic" studied vehicle class-wise speed volume models for heterogenous traffic of six lane divided roads in Chennai city at the mid-block section by using micro- simulation model HETEROSIM which was calibrated according to the observed traffic conditions [3].

Balaji Ponnu et al (2013) in his paper "Vehicle Class-wise Speed Volume model for Three-lane Undivided Urban Roads" found that multi-class speed flow equations are more relevant to these types of facilities rather than single class flow speed models. [4].

Ashish Dhamaniya et al (2013) in his paper "Speed Prediction Models for Urban Arterials under Mixed Traffic Conditions" developed speed density relations for different vehicle type on urban arterial roads under mix traffic conditions in Chandigarh, Jaipur and Delhi using a set of simultaneous equations and established speed prediction models and also compares the manoeuvrability of a vehicle type [5].

Hiren V Patel et al (2013) in his paper "Capacity Determination of an Arterial Road" determined capacity of Modasa town in Gujarat by developing speed flow density relationships which can be helpful for working out improvement plans of the town and finding out the LOS of the road [6].

XU Cheng et al (2014) in his paper "Analysis of Traffic Speed-Density Relation Model Characteristics" compared 10 typical speed density relation models and analysed by parameter calibrations

and fitting errors on Beijing Expressway and found out that out of all, Newell and Logistic models showed good stability [7].

Wang, S. et. Al (2021) [8] and Nicholas B Taylor (2025) [9] developed for model on empirically calibrating stochastic traffic flow fundamental diagram for better understanding the dynamics of speed changes based on volume and time.

3. STUDY AREA AND SURVEY

Kanchrapara, the primary commercial business district (CBD) was selected for the case study area. It is one of the business hubs in North 24 Pargana district of West Bengal, India. And the selected location is one of the busiest road sections in Kanchrapara. Data was collected with the help of video cameras which were placed at the entry and exit of road at selected location. The distance between the entry and exit point is 100 meters. The video started at 9:00 AM and it continued till 9:00 PM. The video was run on a computer and the numbers of vehicles are counted for every minute at entry and exit points. The initial density is 75/1000 vehicles/m. A particular road section was considered for counting the vehicles and 4 poles were kept around the road section (2 poles on the left side and remaining 2 poles on the right side of the road). The length of the section was 5 meters, and the width of the section was 7 meters. The video started at 11.30 AM and it is continued till 12.30 PM. The flow data is calculated at entry and exit points such a way that the vehicles which are passing through the rectangular section in every minute. The exit flow data is considered in the project. The density data is calculated after every 10 sec i.e. the number of vehicles staying in the rectangular section after every 10 sec and then the density data is averaged. The speed data is done by calculating the time the vehicle which enters and exits the rectangular section.

4. METHODOLOGY

Qualitative data analysis and quantitative data have been collected from the study area. In qualitative research using interviews, focus groups, experiments etc. data analysis is going to involve identifying common patterns within the responses and critically analyzing them to achieve research aims and objectives. A graph is drawn in between the average density (vehicle/m) in X-axis and exit flow (vehicle/s) in Y-axis. But the graph is not to point out due to lack of insufficient data points. The collected data for that particular kind of road stretch is of a limited dense it domain. The figure also shows a fitted second order polynomial to the data (which is expected to explain the nature of any flow-density diagram). The maximum of the fitted curve, i.e., the highest flow value indicates capacity of the road stretch. Two cameras were used, one at the entry of vehicle, and another is exit and the distance between to camera is 100 m. After taken the video we analyse the video by using laptop and we take the values from this.

5. RESULT AND ANALYSIS

Data collected from study area have been analyzed and following four graphs have been plotted: Speed vs. Flow relationship (Figure 4), Speed vs. Density relationship (Figure 5), Flow vs. Density relationship (Figure 6) and Speed vs. Flow vs. Density relationship (Figure 7). The data obtained from field have been arranged in Excel and the relationship diagrams have been plotted.

It is observed from Figure 4 that, the flow is maximum at 11:00 AM and at 14:00 which means the number of vehicles passing to the selected two locations is maximum. This is because, maximum offices started from 10:00 am the shops near by the roads also open before 10:00 which make make the traffic flow maximum which mean the travel duration is comparatively lower with respect to the other survey timing. It is also observed from Figure 4 that, at 13:00 the flow is minimum, and it is 300 which means the vehicle takes maximum time to cross the selected 2 points compared to the other survey timing. As the closing of the schools and shops the number of vehicles is maximum currently. Similarly other relationships are also illustrated below:

Figure 4: Speed vs. Flow relationship

Figure 5: Speed vs. Density relationship

Figure 6: Flow vs. Density relationship

It is again observed from Figure 5, Figure 6 and Figure 7 that the density and traffic flow is maximum at 11:00 in the morning and 13:00 in the afternoon. Due to the maximum flow and density, it is obvious that the speed is minimum at 11:00 and 13:00.

Figure 7: Speed vs. Flow vs. Density relationship

6. CONCLUSIONS

- Some measures need to be taken to reduce the flow and density for smooth traffic movement in the selected region. It was observed from the study that operating speed is very low throughout day which creates traffic and slows down the traffic movement in the CBD.
- Speed flow density relationships are very important for finding the existing condition of roads and for planning out the future infrastructure of the road. It is used to find out the capacity of the road by finding these relationships at peak hours and LOS of the road can also be found out. Speed limit for a particular road can also be estimated. It is the basic step to note down the traffic flow pattern of the road and serviceability of the road.
- Data obtained from this study can be effectively used by the traffic and transportation engineers to mitigate the traffic problem in similar type of urban towns.
- A rigorous data collection throughout the year is required for better understanding of the situation in the selected area which is the limitation of the study.
- Based on the collected data, the probabilistic curve can be plotted in future for better understanding of speed deviation with change of traffic volume.
- The results obtained from the study can also be implemented in similar types of urban CBD and presented to the local authorities for modification or upgradation in traffic management.

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